

MODERN THERAPY OF VARIOUS TYPES OF ALLERGODERMATOSIS USING COMPLEX OINTMENT "GOOSE FAT+"

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Abstract. *Allergodermatoses occur on average in 20% of patients with all allergic diseases. These diseases are combined according to the principle of participation in their pathogenesis of allergic developmental mechanisms, the target organ of which is the skin. Despite the variety of etiological factors, mechanisms of development of these diseases, as well as huge clinical differences in localization, morphology of rashes, subjective complaints of the patient, a number of immunological changes are the basis for the implementation of inflammation in the skin. Approaches to the treatment of these diseases are determined by their etiological and pathogenetic mechanisms of development and consist in the implementation of elimination measures, the use of both systemic and external pharmacotherapy.*

Keywords: *allergodermatoses, atopic dermatitis, allergic contact dermatitis, external therapy, goose fat.*

Currently, there has been a significant increase and widespread distribution of allergic dermatoses [1–3]. The development of complications in these diseases predetermined the interest in improving external therapy. Violation of the skin barrier, an increase in transepidermal water loss, and a change in pH lead to a decrease in the protective mechanisms of the skin, as a result of which there is an increased susceptibility of the skin to infections [4]. Changes in the skin microbiota contribute to constant sensitization of the body due to the antigenic activity of microbial superantigens [5]. Superantigens of *Staphylococcus aureus* stimulate Langerhans cells and T-cell proliferation, and also act as allergens that increase inflammation, which leads to a decrease in the barrier function of the skin, promotes secondary infection, the spread of bacterial and fungal infections. Complications, caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* are among the most common in allergic dermatoses [6–8]. Thus, atopic dermatitis is accompanied by an overgrowth of *Staphylococcus aureus* [9]. The prevalence of bacterial infection has a positive correlation with the duration of the disease and the severity of itching [10]. The high incidence of secondary infection of allergic dermatoses, disorders of innate and adaptive immunity maintain a chronic course, contribute to a decrease in the quality of life of patients. The course of secondary pyoderma is well known, accompanied by an increase in the inflammatory reaction, pustulization, the spread of serous-purulent and purulent hemorrhagic crusts on the surface and along the periphery. atopic dermatitis is accompanied by overgrowth of *Staphylococcus aureus* [9]. The prevalence of bacterial infection has a positive correlation with the duration of the disease and the severity of itching [10]. The high incidence of secondary infection of allergic dermatoses, disorders of innate and adaptive immunity maintain a chronic course, contribute to a decrease in the quality of life of patients. The course of secondary pyoderma is well known, accompanied by an increase in the inflammatory reaction, pustulization, the spread of serous-purulent and purulent hemorrhagic crusts on the surface and along the periphery. atopic dermatitis is accompanied by overgrowth of

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Despite the fact that allergic dermatoses are polyetiological and multifactorial diseases and their treatment requires an integrated approach, external therapy occupies a major place in the treatment of these diseases. Rational external therapy eliminates the inflammatory reaction and subjective sensations of itching, pain, burning; reduce violations of the epidermal barrier and protect the skin from adverse environmental factors, stimulate reparative processes in the skin, and control the addition of a secondary bacterial and fungal infection.

In order to assess the effectiveness and safety of a complex ointment with the addition of goose fat in the form of a cream and ointment, its effect and tolerability were compared in various forms of allergic dermatoses.

Materials and methods

Inclusion criteria for this study were:

- clinical signs of atopic dermatitis or true eczema in the acute stage;
- the severity of atopic dermatitis from 20 to 60 points SCORAD or the severity of true eczema from 20 to 50 points EASI;
- age over 2 years.

The exclusion criteria were:

- state of erythroderma;
- hypersensitivity to the components of the drugs used;
- age under 2 years;
- the presence of any condition that may create an unreasonable risk of harm to the health of the patient;
- therapy with systemic glucocorticoid agents, during the previous 4 weeks;
- Topical corticosteroid therapy within the previous 3 weeks.

During the study, it was mandatory to record any adverse events for further evaluation of the safety of study drugs. Under our supervision in the main group were 62 patients aged 17 to 35 years, including 31 women, 31 men. Atopic dermatitis was diagnosed in 34 patients, true eczema - in 28 patients. The duration of the disease ranged from 3 months to 15 years. All patients had previously received repeated courses of treatment, including antihistamines, desensitizing agents, topical preparations containing glucocorticoids, naftalan, 4 patients had previously received

physiotherapy in the form of ultrahigh-frequency therapy. At the time of examination, all had signs of exacerbation of the skin process, increased itching, and sleep disorders.

- itching of the skin,
- age-related changes in characteristic skin lesions,
- chronic relapsing course,
- the presence of atopic diseases in the patient and / or his relatives,
- start at an early age
- seasonal exacerbations,
- exacerbation of the process under the influence of provoking factors (allergens, irritants, foods, emotional stress),
- dry skin,
- white dermographism,
- susceptibility to skin infections,
- cheilitis,
- Denier-Morgan sign
- hyperpigmentation of the skin of the periorbital region, - an increase in the content of total and allergen-specific IgE in serum,
- eosinophilia of peripheral blood.

Therapeutic components of goose fat:

- Polyunsaturated fatty acids - provide normal metabolism and metabolism in tissues, increase the immune system in the skin, accelerate tissue regeneration, naturally moisturize the skin and make it more elastic.

- Omega 3 (oleic acid) - renews and rejuvenates tissues;

- Omega 6 (linoleic acid) - restores protective functions, has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory functions, slows down moisture loss.

- Vitamin E (tocopherol) - slows down the aging process of tissues, normalizes blood circulation and microcirculation in the upper layers of the skin, increases cell regeneration, helps get rid of scars, smooths wrinkles.

-Vitamins of group B - increase metabolic processes in skin cells, improve the penetration of nutrients to them.

- Selenium - gives the skin elasticity and velvety, smooths wrinkles, relieves itching and irritation.

- Sodium - maintains normal water balance in the skin;

- Magnesium - improves metabolic processes in cells, slows down their aging;

-Zinc - reduces redness and irritation, normalizes the sebaceous glands, improves tissue healing.

Results and its discussion

All patients showed a pronounced decrease in itching, erythema, and swelling on the 3rd day of using the natural remedy "GOOSE FAT +". In the future, the regression of rashes gradually continued. By the 6th day of treatment, the state of health of all patients improved, itching decreased. After 7-10 days of application of "GOOSE FAT +" there was a complete regression of acute inflammation, night sleep was restored. On the 12-15th day, all patients showed a significant improvement. After treatment in DIQI improved and amounted to 7.8 ± 5.5 . SCORAD decreased to 8 ± 1.0 . EASI decreased to 7.1 ± 0.5

Conclusions

Therapy was well tolerated by all patients, no adverse reactions or adverse events were noted in any case. Also, there was no negative effect of the therapy on the indicators of peripheral blood, urine. The results obtained by us confirm the previously described high therapeutic efficacy and safety of the use of the natural remedy "GOOSE FAT +" based on goose fat in allergic dermatoses. Having no side effects, "GOOSE FAT +" was easily used in patients.

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